

Structural insights into the evolution of alpha/beta-hydrolase fold luciferases

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ABSTRACT

The α/β -hydrolase (ABH) superfamily is a widespread and functionally versatile protein fold recognized for its ability to adapt to diverse molecular functions across all three domains of life. One such spectacular example of evolutionary adaptation at the ABH fold is an acquisition of oxygenolytic luciferase reaction that occurred within the hydrolytic haloalkane dehalogenase family. The molecular details of this evolution remain puzzling. In this work, we determine crystal structures and explore dynamical behaviour of a bifunctional ancestral ABH-fold enzyme, highlighting molecular features associated with the transition from hydrolytic to oxygenolytic catalysis at this fold. Structures showed a canonical $\alpha\beta$ -sandwich shielded with a helical cap domain. The catalytic pocket is voluminous enough to accommodate a bulky substrate. Molecular dynamics simulations demonstrated that coelenterazine entry does not present a major energetic barrier and identified a preferred binding orientation important for oxygenolytic catalysis. Comparisons between ancestral and extant enzymes highlighted specific amino acids and sequence motifs characteristic for oxygenolytic luciferases. Collectively, our results provide an expanded view of the evolutionary transition in which ABH-fold enzymes, originally using water to cleave chemical bonds, adapted to utilize dioxygen for bioluminescence.

1. Introduction

The α/β -hydrolase (ABH) fold represents a structurally adaptable scaffold that supports a broad spectrum of catalytic functions, including hydrolytic dehalogenation and oxidative bioluminescence. This fold forms the structural basis for both haloalkane dehalogenases (HLDs) [1–3] and *Renilla*-type luciferases [4,5], despite their drastically distinct chemistries and substrate specificities. For this reason, the ABH fold has emerged as an ideal template not only for studying the evolution of new enzymatic functions but also for protein engineering platforms aimed at expanding enzymatic function, stability, and catalytic efficiency.

The evolution of luciferase activity from a dehalogenase scaffold is thought to involve the adaptation of structural features, particularly within the cap domain and substrate-binding tunnel, to accommodate the bulkier and more hydrophobic coelenterazine (CTZ) substrate and facilitate photon emission [6,7]. Advances in ancestral sequence

reconstruction (ASR) have enabled the reconstruction and engineering of proteins that bridge these two functional classes, providing snapshots of evolutionary intermediates and versatile templates for biotechnological applications [6,8]. Recent discovery of the first extant enzyme with both luciferase and HLD activity further supports the hypothesis of luminescence evolving from a dehalogenase-like ancestor [9].

Among ancestral sequences, dual-function enzymes such as Anc^{HLD-RLuc} [6] and its engineered variant Anc^{INS} [7] have been studied for their ability to catalyze both dehalogenation and bioluminescence reactions. These proteins offer unique opportunities to dissect the molecular basis of functional divergence and to rationally engineer catalytic efficiency and stability. Another ancestral protein, DhaA 238Loc, exhibits substantially enhanced luciferase activity while retaining dehalogenase function [10]. While DhaA 238Loc is similar (72.9% identity, 84.4% similarity) to previously reported Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, its bioluminescence is improved (4.8-fold increase), but the structural determinants

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responsible for this improvement remain uncharacterized. Understanding how active site and aromatic core configurations contribute to the dehalogenase-to-luciferase catalysis shift is essential not only for elucidating enzyme evolution but also for advancing the rational design of improved luciferase reporters for imaging, diagnostics, and biosensing.

In this study, we determine crystal structures of DhaA 238Loc, the dual-function ancestral enzyme capable of catalyzing both hydrolytic dehalogenase and oxygenolytic luciferase activity with improved performance. Through a comprehensive structural and dynamical comparison between ancestral and extant ABH-fold enzymes, we attempt to identify and map key residues and molecular elements driving the acquisition of oxygenolytic bioluminescent reaction at this fold. Moreover, we identify residue-level adaptations that distinguish luciferase-active enzymes from the evolutionary original hydrolytic HLDs (Fig. 1). By delineating these structural determinants, we seek to improve understanding of enzyme adaptation, inform future engineering efforts, and advance the development of enhanced bioluminescent tools.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. DNA mutagenesis

A four-point point mutant variant of DhaA 238Loc was prepared, containing mutations V146I/V147R/S145F/H142C, hereafter referred as DhaA 238Loc^{Mut}. Substitutions at identified positions were selected based on the template *DhaA* gene. Mutagenesis was carried out using MegaPrimer Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) technique [11] using forward primer (5'-GATCGTGTAAAGCAATTGTTGCATGGAATTATTCGTCAGCCGATTCGCTAGCTGGGAAACCTG-3') and reverse primer: 5'-GCTAGTTATTGCTCAGCGG-3'. The newly created sequence was verified by DNA-sequencing, confirming the presence of the intended mutations.

2.2. Protein overproduction and purification

E. coli BL21(DE3) pre-culture carrying pET21b plasmid containing DhaA 238Loc or DhaA 238Loc^{Mut} gene [10] was cultivated in LB medium containing 100 µg/mL ampicillin at 37 °C for 4 h. Expression of main culture was induced with 0.5 mM IPTG followed by incubation at 20 °C for 16 h. Harvested cells were resuspended in buffer (50 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 10 mM Tris, pH 7.5) and stored at -70 °C. Following thawing and DNase treatment, cells were lysed by sonication and the

lysate clarified by centrifugation (21,036 ×g, 4 °C, 1 h) and 0.45 µm filtration. Purification of the protein was carried out in two steps. First, affinity chromatography was performed using an ÄKTA Pure system (Cytiva, USA) equipped with a 5-mL HisTrap™ excel column (Cytiva, USA). The protein was eluted with a buffer containing 50 mM NaCl, 350 mM imidazole, and 10 mM Tris (pH 7.5). In the second step, gel filtration was conducted using a HiLoad 16/600 Superdex 200 pg column (Cytiva, USA) on the ÄKTA Pure system with a buffer composed of 50 mM NaCl and 10 mM Tris (pH 7.5). Finally, the protein size and purity were verified by SDS-PAGE.

2.3. Circular dichroism spectroscopy

To assess the secondary structure and conformational integrity of the purified enzymes, circular dichroism (CD) spectra were recorded at room temperature using a Chirascan spectropolarimeter (Applied Photophysics, Leatherhead, UK) equipped with a Peltier thermostat. Samples were prepared in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.5). Spectra were collected from 190 to 280 nm at a scan rate of 100 nm•min⁻¹ with a 0.5 s response time and a 1 nm bandwidth using a 0.5 mm quartz cuvette. Each spectrum shown represents an average of three scans and was baseline-corrected using the buffer signal. CD data were expressed in terms of the mean residue ellipticity (ΘMRE).

2.4. Thermal unfolding measurements

Thermal stability and unfolding were assessed using both NanoDSF Prometheus (NanoTemper, DE) and Chirascan spectropolarimeter (Applied Photophysics, UK). The NanoDSF analysis was based on monitoring intrinsic tryptophan fluorescence across a temperature range of 20–95 °C with a heating rate of 1 °C•min⁻¹. Measurements were conducted in triplicate, with sample concentrations of approximately 1 mg•mL⁻¹. The T_m values were determined using ThermControl v2.0.2 software. Finally, the average values and standard deviations were calculated.

For Chirascan spectropolarimeter analysis, thermal stability was evaluated by monitoring the ellipticity at 222 nm over a temperature range of 20–95 °C at 0.1 nm resolution and a heating rate of 1 °C•min⁻¹. The resulting thermal denaturation curves were roughly normalised to the fraction of unfolded protein (f_u) by defining native and denatured baselines via linear extrapolation. The apparent melting temperature ($T_{m, app}$) was determined by fitting the normalised data to a two-state Boltzmann sigmoidal model, representing the midpoint of the thermal

Fig. 1. The evolution of luciferase activity within the ABH-fold protein family. (a-c) Gallery of active-site cavity volumes ranging from purely hydrolytic HLDs (DhaA) to specialized luciferases (RLuc). The path progresses through dual-function enzyme prototypes, (i) Anc^{HLD-RLuc} and (ii) DhaA 238Loc, which possess latent oxygenolytic activity alongside their primary dehalogenase function. (b) Comparative illustration of the reciprocal shifts in HLD and LUC catalytic activities across the proposed evolutionary trajectory.

transition.

2.5. Halide oxidation assay

Dehalogenase activity of the enzymes was measured using halide oxidation (HOX) assay [12]. The enzymatic reactions were performed in quadruplicate at room temperature in POVb buffer (1 mM orthovanadate, 20 mM phosphate buffer, pH = 8.0), which also served as the negative control. Each reaction was initiated by mixing 80 μL of a primary solution (12.5 $\text{U}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ histagged *Curvularia inaequalis* vanadium chloroperoxidase (CiVCPO), 12.5 mM H_2O_2 and 62.5 μM APF) with 20 μL of a secondary solution containing 0.28 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ enzyme. This was followed by the automated injection of 100 μL of 1,2-dibromoethane (DBE) substrate (0.2% v/v) to reach final reaction concentrations 5 $\text{U}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ CiVCPO, 5 mM H_2O_2 , 25 μM APF, 0.028 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ enzyme and 0.1% v/v DBE. Fluorescence was monitored using a CLARIOstar Plus plate reader (BMG Labtech, Germany) equipped with a linear variable filter (LVF) monochromator set at 483–14/530–30 nm (excitation/emission) and a 502.5 nm dichroic filter. The gain and optical focal height were determined automatically by the system prior to data acquisition.

2.6. Luciferase activity measurement

The concentration of enzymes was determined spectrophotometrically (DS-11 Spectrophotometer, DeNovix, USA) as 19 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ for DhaA 238Loc and 16.5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ for DhaA 238Loc^{Mut}. For the luminescence measurement, the baseline luminescence signal was measured on 25 μL of enzyme (5 s, gain 2200), using a FLUOstar Omega microplate reader (BMG Labtech, Germany). A 225 μL of assay buffer (100 mM potassium phosphate, 1 mM Na_2SO_4 , pH = 7.5) supplemented with 8.8 μM coelenterazine was added to the enzyme, and luminescence was measured immediately for 5 s. All measurements were repeated 4 times, and the average activity with standard deviation was determined for all variants as $\text{RLU}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{mg}^{-1}$.

2.7. Protein crystallization

Freshly purified protein was concentrated to approximately 10 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$, and crystallization screenings were performed using a Gryphon LCP crystallization robot (Art Robbins Instruments, USA). The sitting-drop vapor-diffusion method was set up in 96-well plates (SWISSCI, CH) with 1:1 or 1:2 precipitant-to-protein ratios, and plates were incubated at 20 °C. Crystal formation was observed after 1–2 weeks. Diffraction-quality crystals were obtained in two conditions (Table S1) from the Morpheus screen (Molecular Dimensions, UK). Crystals were cryo-cooled by flash freezing in liquid nitrogen for X-ray diffraction analysis.

2.8. X-ray data collection and structure refinement

X-ray diffraction data were collected at the Swiss Light Source synchrotron using a PXIII beamline with a wavelength of 1.0 Å. Data processing was carried out using XDS [13] and scaling was performed with Aimless [14]. Structures were determined by molecular replacement using Phaser [15] with the AlphaFold2-predicted model (ColabFold v1.5.5) [16] as a search template. Several cycles of automatic refinement in Phenix [17] and manual refinement in Coot [18] were performed. Ligands were built using eLBOW [19], and the final structures were graphically visualized with the PyMOL Molecular Graphics System (Version 3.1 Schrödinger, LLC).

2.9. Bioinformatic analysis

Protein structures were aligned in the PyMOL Molecular Graphics System (Version 3.1, Schrödinger, LLC Chain A was used in all cases.

Protein sequences were analyzed and aligned using Clustal Omega Multiple Sequence Alignment [20] and visualized with ESPript 3.0 [21]. The active site cavity volumes were calculated using FPocketWeb 1.0.1 [22,23] and CAVER Analyst 2.0 [24] for each chain., List of all used PDB IDs can be found in Table S2 and all aligned protein sequences are summarized in Table S3. Calculations of root mean square deviation (RMSD) between protein structures were calculated using the Dali server [25]. Publication-quality figures were created in <https://BioRender.com>.

2.10. Structure preparation and molecular docking

Ligand structures for coelenterazine (CTZ, substrate) and coelenteramide (CEL, product) were built and optimized in Avogadro 1.2.0 [26]. Atomic charges and parameters were generated using the R.E.D. Server Development 2.0 [45] and AmberTools16 [27]. The crystal structure of DhaA 238Loc was aligned in PyMOL (Schrödinger, LLC) to a reference template (PDB ID: 2psf; [4]), and protonation states were assigned via the H++ web server [28]. Molecular docking was performed with AutoDock Vina 1.1.2 [29] using an exhaustiveness of 100 to sample the conformational space thoroughly.

2.11. Adaptive steered molecular dynamics

To investigate the entry pathways of CTZ, we employed Adaptive Steered Molecular Dynamics (ASMD) [30]. Systems were described using the ff14SB protein force field [31] and TIP3P water model [32]. Following a multi-step minimization and equilibration protocol in PMEMD.CUDA [33], we simulated the binding process by steering the CTZ substrate toward the catalytic residue D120. We utilized a pulling approach across 25 parallel replicas per epoch, and the Jarzynski average [34] was used to identify the most representative trajectories for subsequent stages. Four different starting orientations were used (Fig. S7): one, leading to the potentially reactive conformation similar to the co-crystallized substrate in AncFT-L14; and three, rotated horizontally, vertically, or both for 180 degrees, which leads to potentially non-reactive binding.

2.12. Adaptive sampling and Markov state modelling

Product release was simulated using an adaptive sampling method implemented within the HTMD3 computational package [35]. Starting from the ASMD-derived bound state, we generated a cumulative 10 μs of MD trajectories, comprising 20 epochs of 10 parallel MD simulations. To process this data, we first reduced the dimensionality of the conformational space using time-lagged independent component analysis (tICA), focusing on the distance between CEI and the catalytic D120 residue [36]. This projected space was then clustered into 1000 discrete microstates using the k-means clustering algorithm to provide a framework for Markov State Model (MSM) construction. Macrostates were defined at lag times of 15–17 ns to characterize the transition of CEI between bound, tunnel, and unbound states. Model validity was confirmed via Chapman-Kolmogorov tests.

2.13. Kinetic analysis

Kinetic parameters, including association and dissociation rates (k_{on} , k_{off}), mean first-passage times (MFPT), and the equilibrium dissociation constant (KD), were computed using the HTMD3 kinetics module [35]. The analysis modeled transitions between the “unbound” (source) and “bound” (sink) macrostates. To ensure statistical reliability, we performed bootstrapping (100 iterations on 80% of the data) to calculate average kinetic values and their associated standard deviations.

2.14. Binding energy calculations

Binding free energies (ΔG_{bind}) and per-residue interaction decompositions were calculated using the molecular mechanics/generalized Born surface area (MM/GBSA) method [37,38]. Calculations were performed using the MMPBSA.py module of AmberTools [27] on 100 snapshots extracted from both the “bound” and “tunnel” macrostates. The systems were modeled using an implicit generalized Born solvent environment with a salt concentration of 0.1 M.

2.15. Tunnel and cavity analysis

Access tunnels in the dynamic protein structures were characterized using CAVER Analyst 2.0 [24] and the CAVER 3.01 algorithm [39]. We analyzed 1000 snapshots from the “unbound” state to identify pathways leading to the active site. These results were compared to previously established tunnel profiles of related enzymes, including RLuc8 and AncFT-L14 [40] to analyse the transport efficiency of DhaA 238Loc.

Full details regarding computational setup, simulation parameters, and specific software modules are provided in the **Supplementary Information**.

3. Results

3.1. Protein crystallization outcomes

Our production and purification procedures gained highly pure and properly folded DhaA 238 Loc protein, possessing a high thermal stability ($T_m = 70.5 \pm 0.03$ °C), suitable for crystallization screenings (Fig. 2). While many crystals exhibited poor diffraction, high-resolution data were obtained for two structures in distinct space groups: C121 and

P2₁2₁2 (Table S4). Both final models contain two enzyme molecules in the asymmetric unit. The C121 structure was selected for further analysis due to its higher completeness (Fig. S2). The P2₁2₁2 structure showed missing electron density in the L9 loop (residues 151–156), suggesting localized flexibility (Fig. S1). In both structures, additional electron density in the active site was interpreted as polyethylene glycol (PEG) molecules, originating from the mother liquor.

3.2. Overall structure of DhaA 238Loc

Similar to previously described HLD-fold enzymes [3,7,41], DhaA 238Loc features a central α/β -hydrolase core domain and a four-helix cap domain (α_4 , α_5' , α_5 , α_6 , and α_7) anchored by the L9 and L14 loops. (Fig. 3a). The active site is located in a hydrophobic cavity between these domains and contains the conserved catalytic amino acids (Fig. 3a-c) conserved within the HLD-II subfamily, including a nucleophilic aspartate (Asp120), a histidine base (His286), and a catalytic acid (Glu144). Together, these form a proton relay system characteristic of this enzyme family. Two halide-stabilizing residues (Asn53 and Trp121) are also present in the active site cavity. In RLuc, these residues mediate the stabilization of molecular oxygen and the leaving carbon dioxide during the catalysis. In chain A of DhaA 238Loc, halide-stabilizing residues are involved in specific interactions with the PEG molecule. These residues are conserved across the enzyme family and are known to stabilize a halide ion in HLDs, or molecular oxygen and the leaving carbon dioxide in RLuc.

The structure consists of two molecules, chains A and B (RMSD = 0.8 Å), exhibiting conformational differences driven by the length of their bound PEG molecules. In chain B, the α_4 helix shifts and Phe164 “flips out” of the active site to accommodate the longer PEG, whereas it stays “flipped-in” in chain A. Rotational shifts in the Phe262/Phe263 dyad,

Fig. 2. Biophysical characterization of DhaA 238Loc. (a) Gel filtration elution profile and SDS-PAGE gel of eluted peak fractions. (b) Diffracting-quality DhaA 238Loc crystals obtained in Morpheus screen (Molecular Dimensions, UK) in well H5 (top photo) and H8 (bottom photo). (c, d) NanoDSF measurement of thermal stability shown as ratio of integrated fluorescence (c) and first derivative of thermal unfolding curve (d).

Fig. 3. Structural comparison of DhaA 238Loc and AncFT. Crystal structure of DhaA 238Loc with bound PEG (light violet) is shown in comparison to AncFT (pale green) with bound CEI (magenta). (a) Catalytic pentad residues are highlighted as spheres: yellow in DhaA 238Loc and dark green in AncFT. Overall structures: (i) DhaA 238Loc, (ii) AncFT, (iii) front view and (iv) side view of the superposition of DhaA 238Loc and AncFT. (b) $2F_o - F_c$ electron density map (contour level 1σ) of the bound PEG in DhaA 238Loc, (c) superposition of the catalytic sites of DhaA 238Loc (with PEG) and AncFT (with CEI), and (d) detailed view of PEG binding in DhaA 238Loc.

Trp156, and Phe181 (Fig. 4) further highlight active-site plasticity.

3.3. Structural adaptations toward luciferase activity

Beyond the conserved core architecture, several structural adaptations appear to distinguish luciferases from typical HLDs. The valine dyad (V146-V147) containing small side chains is conserved across all compared luciferase-active proteins, except for Afluc featuring an M155-C156 dyad (Fig. 5b, 6). In contrast, aligned HLDs lack this valine motif. DmmA and DmmarA exhibit a Leu-Val and DspA a Val-Tyr sequence, while other tested HLDs possess bulkier residues such as Ile/Leu/Cys in place of Val146 and Cys/Leu/Tyr/Ala/Arg in place of Val147 (Fig. 5a).

Further differentiation occurs in the α_4 helix. While Asp162 is conserved in most luciferases, in DhaA 238Loc it is shifted by one position in the tertiary structure compared to RLuc8 and AncFT (Fig. 5a, b). At its position, isoleucine Ile163 is found instead.

His142 is conserved among all aligned luciferase-active enzymes. In contrast, typical HLDs, except for DspA, possess hydrophobic residues at this position, (Ile, Tyr, Phe, or Cys).

Similarly, Ser145 is conserved among enzymes displaying luciferase activity. In contrast, HLDs feature other polar residues at the Ser145 position: Gly in DspA, Ala in DhA/LinB/DmmA/DmmarA, and Phe in DhaA/DbjA/DbeA, forming a compact hydrophobic core. This environment is comprised of a network of hydrophobic residues including (residue numbers refer to DhaA 238Loc in alignment): Phe127 (Leu in DhA and Met in DmmA), Ile/Val/Leu/Phe at position 270 (however Gly

in RLuc8), Ile/Leu/Val at position 140, Phe/Tyr/Arg/Leu at position 255, and Trp/Cys/Val/Leu at position 274.

Leu/Ile is conserved at position 167 in equivalent position in all aligned luciferase-active enzymes and HLDs DspA, DmmA, and DmmarA (Fig. 5b and Fig. 6). The Phe181 occupies the equivalent site in LinB, DhaA, DbeA, and DbjA, while in DhA, it is replaced by Trp. In its proximity, Phe181 is conserved at the equivalent position in all compared luciferases and dual-function ancestral enzymes, except for Afluc, where it is substituted by a tyrosine. In other HLDs, with the exception of DmmA, this site is occupied by a smaller non-aromatic residues such as Glu, Met, Val, or Ala.

3.4. Presence of the aromatic core

The tightly packed cluster of aromatic residues lines the substrate-binding pocket. Position equivalent to 156 in DhaA 238Loc varies between some luciferases and HLDs (Fig. 7a, b). In DhaA 238Loc, AncFT, RLuc, and DhaA, this position is occupied by a tryptophan. In contrast, Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, AncINS, DafA, Afluc, DhA, DspA, LinB, DmmAR, DbjA, and DbeA all feature a phenylalanine at the same site. The presence of Met183 in DmmA highlights the structural diversity at this position, though its impact on the lack of luciferase activity in this scaffold remains to be determined. Efficient luciferases such as AncFT, AncINS, RLuc8, and Afluc lack bulky Phe164, featuring instead smaller residues at the corresponding position: Ile163 in AncFT, Leu162 in AncINS, Ile161 in RLuc (Fig. 7b), and Leu173 in Afluc. In contrast, other compared HLDs and low-activity ancestors retain phenylalanine, or

Fig. 4. Conformational changes between DhaA 238Loc chains A and B. PEG from chain A is shown in dark violet, PEG from chain B is shown in pale violet.

long-chain methionine (Met137) in DmmarA, suggesting a potential link between residue bulk at this position and catalytic efficiency.

Notably, the conserved Phe262/Phe263 dyad in DhaA 238Loc is distinctive to the studied luciferases, whereas compared HLDs feature aliphatic residues (e.g., Ala-Leu, Val-Met) (Fig. 6). These bulky aromatic side chains are positioned to create a compact, hydrophobic microenvironment conducive to efficient CTZ binding. Notably, in chain B of the DhaA 238Loc structure, Phe263 adopts an inward-facing conformation triggered by a bound PEG that mirrors the orientation seen in the RLuc8 structure (PDB ID: 7OMO, [5]).

3.5. Voluminous enzymatic pocket accommodates bulky luciferin

All structural features and differences described above collectively contribute to differences in the active site cavity volumes. When comparing these volumes, ABH-fold luciferases generally have larger active site cavities than HLDs (Fig. 8g-i). This molecular adaptation is consistent with the requirement for a larger volume to accommodate the bulky CTZ molecule during the bioluminescent reaction. Notable exceptions to this trend are DbjA and Dmma, two HLDs that display cavity volumes comparable to luciferases.

3.6. Cavity volume assessment

To assess whether CTZ and CEI can be accommodated within the catalytic cavities of the studied proteins, we performed rigid-receptor molecular docking. While the predicted poses of CTZ and CEI in RLuc8 and AncFT-L14 resembled the crystallographic luciferins (CEI, [5]), the poses in DhaA 238Loc significantly differ. However, they still fit in the catalytic site (Figs. S3–5, Table S5). In Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, both CTZ and CEI did not fit the active site and were docked on the surface at the tunnel entrance. Given that docking did not consistently reproduce crystallographic poses across all systems, the results are interpreted here

only as a qualitative indication of cavity complementarity. The full docking analysis is provided in the Supplementary Information for completeness. To supplement the docking results, we used CAVER Analyst 2.0 [24] to calculate the cavity volumes. The chain with the larger active site cavity volume was labelled as “open” and smaller as “closed” states. The active site cavity in DhaA 238Loc is more spacious than Anc^{HLD-RLuc} but still smaller than in RLuc8 (Fig. S6).

3.7. Substrate binding is energetically favourable

We simulated substrate binding using adaptive steered MD (ASMD). Among four starting orientations tested (Fig. S7), pose 1 leading to a potentially reactive binding (conformation similar to co-crystallised substrate in the structure PDB ID 7ome) was the most accessible (Fig. 8b), consistent with prior results for RLuc8 and AncFT-L14. Notably, the substrate binds most easily to AncFT-L14, closely followed by DhaA 238Loc (1.9 kcal·mol⁻¹ difference), while RLuc required 5 kcal·mol⁻¹ more work than DhaA 238Loc (Fig. 8a). In contrast, CTZ binding to Anc^{HLD-RLuc} required almost twice as much work as to RLuc8, and the preferred starting pose was “flipped” compared to the crystal pose (Fig. S8). These results suggest that limited activity in DhaA 238Loc is unlikely due to geometrically unfavorable substrate binding or a high-energy barrier of substrate transport.

3.8. Product release is hampered

CEI release was studied using adaptive sampling MD from both the crystallographic pose and the “flipped” Anc^{HLD-RLuc} pose. Notably, the crystal-like pose of CEI in Anc^{HLD-RLuc} was not observed experimentally nor predicted by ASMD. Therefore, it was created artificially by transplanting CEI from the crystal structure of AncFT (PDB ID 7qxq) and should be interpreted rather qualitatively. The simulations were clustered to separate the “bound” CEI state, the “tunnel” state (CEI in the

Fig. 5. Structural comparison of key residues distinguishing oxygenolytic luciferases from hydrolytic HLDs. Residues from hydrolytic haloalkane dehalogenases are shown in shades of yellow to red (panel a), whereas residues from luciferase-active proteins are depicted in shades of blue to green (panel b). Panels (a) and (b) compare DhaA 238Loc with representative HLDs and luciferases, respectively. Close-up views (insets *i-iv*) highlight residues with structural adaptations linked to luciferase activity as spheres.

access tunnel), and the “unbound” CEI state (Figs. S9–10, Table S6), and to calculate their equilibrium probabilities (Fig. 8c), and estimate kinetics (Table S7).

As reported previously by Toul and co-workers [40], the simulations have indicated that the product release is energetically favorable in RLuc8 and AncFT-L14, as evidenced by a “bound” state with low equilibrium probability and positive ΔG , k_{off} faster than k_{on} ; Fig. 8c and Tables S3–4. On the other hand, the result of the simulations with Anc^{HLD-RLuc} depended heavily on the product's orientation: the crystal-like pose followed the same trend as RLuc8 and AncFT-L14 with a stronger preference for the “unbound” state, while the energetically preferred flipped pose followed the opposite trend, which might explain previously observed product inhibition [7]. Interestingly, in DhaA 238Loc, we also observed strong product binding in the active site “bound” state, having a 95% equilibrium probability and ΔG of -2.56 kcal·mol⁻¹, indicating slower product release.

In the “bound” macrostates, the product mainly interacted with the same residues in RLuc8 and AncFT-L14, except for Trp156 and Asp162, which lacked a significant affinity in AncFT-L14 (Fig. 8e). The interactions in DhaA 238Loc were also quite similar to RLuc8, the main differences being a lower affinity of the product to Ser145, a higher affinity to Trp156, Phe163 (corresponding to Ile163 in RLuc8), and Pro220, and a significant interaction with Gln148 (Asp148 in RLuc8), which was not detected in RLuc8 or AncFT-L14.

However, the “tunnel” macrostates showed key differences (Fig. S10). In RLuc8, the product interacted with the dynamical L9/ α 4 fragment (Fig. S9) during release, while in a more rigid AncFT-L14, it left straight through the main tunnel. In contrast, in the simulation with DhaA 238Loc, the product leaves through the side (slot) tunnel, which is opened due to the dynamic loop L9. Therefore, the per-residue interactions differ noticeably (Fig. 8f). In RLuc8, the product interacts mainly with Leu165, Ile166, Phe180, Phe181, Pro220, and Ile223; in AncFT-L14 with Ile159, Ile166, Phe180, Phe181, Leu185 (Val185 in RLuc8), and Phe261; while in DhaA 238Loc with Trp156, Pro157, Phe261, and Phe262, which are the residues surrounding the side tunnel.

3.9. Anatomies of enzyme access tunnels

Analysis of access tunnels using CAVER Analyst 2.0 across 1000 “unbound” snapshots showed that all four studied enzymes maintained a main tunnel and a side tunnel (Fig. 8d). RLuc8 and AncFT-L14 had wider main tunnels (average bottleneck radii 2.6 Å and 2.5 Å), while DhaA 238Loc and Anc^{HLD-RLuc} were narrower (both 2.0 Å). Side tunnels were more frequently present in DhaA 238Loc and Anc^{HLD-RLuc} (97% and 95%), and less in RLuc8 and AncFT-L14 (75% and 33%), with corresponding bottleneck radii of 1.43, 1.60, 1.27, and 0.98 Å, respectively. These results fit well with the “tunnel” state in which the ligand interacts

Fig. 6. Multiple sequence protein alignment of DhaA 238Loc and selected proteins: HLDs (LinB, Dh1A, DspA, DhaA, DbjA, DbeA, DmmarA), luciferases (RLuc8, Afluc) and dual function enzymes (DafA, Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, AncFT, AncINS). Amino acids of the putative conserved active site are marked with green stars, the amino acids distinguishing between enzymes with only luciferase activity and HLD/dual function enzymes are marked with yellow arrows.

mainly with residues forming the slot tunnel rather than the main tunnel (Fig. 8f and Fig. S10).

3.10. Experimental validation

To empirically verify the functional roles of the residues identified in

our structural analysis, we generated and characterized the quadruple mutant variant DhaA238LocMut (Fig. 9a), containing mutations V146I/V147R/S145F/H142C. We confirmed the high purity and homogeneity of the purified protein using SDS-PAGE (Fig. 9b), and subsequent Circular Dichroism (CD) spectra measurements verified that the secondary structure remained largely intact (Fig. 9c). The slight differences

Fig. 7. Structural comparison of aromatic core residues differing between luciferases and HLDs. Residues from hydrolytic haloalkane dehalogenases are shown in shades of yellow to red (panel a), whereas residues from luciferase-active proteins are depicted in shades of blue to green (panel b). Panels (a) and (b) compare DhaA 238Loc with representative HLDs and luciferases, respectively, highlighting residues of the aromatic core as spheres (insets i-iii).

observed in the α -helical content of the mutant variant are consistent with the location of the four mutation points. Further, nanoDSF analysis confirmed proper protein folding, showing a single inflection point, although the mutations destabilized the enzyme, reducing its thermostability ($\Delta T_m = 9.3^\circ$) (Fig. 9d, g). Most importantly, biochemical assays revealed that the luciferase activity of the mutant substantially decreased to 2% of the template DhaA 238Loc activity (100%) (Fig. 9e). This significant loss of function confirms the critical role of these specific amino acids in the bioluminescence. Additionally, we observed a 12% decrease in dehalogenase activity (Fig. 9f), suggesting that while these residues are essential for the evolved luciferase function, they also influence the original hydrolytic HLD scaffold.

4. Discussion

In this study, we present structural and dynamical insights into the bifunctional ancestral enzyme DhaA 238Loc, which exhibits dual dehalogenase-luciferase catalysis. DhaA 238Loc adopts the canonical ABH fold, characteristic of both HLDs and *Renilla*-type luciferases. It features a central β -sheet flanked by α -helices, and a cap domain that forms a large active site cavity. PEG molecule, originating from the crystallization mother liquor, bound within the protein cavity, illustrates the accessibility and ligand-accommodating nature of this pocket.

The presence of dual activity in DhaA 238Loc supports the hypothesis that *Renilla*-type luciferases evolved from ABH-fold ancestors with dehalogenase activity [9,42,43]. Similarly, a recent study demonstrated the evolutionary adaptation of a distinct hydrolytic ABH-fold enzyme, 1-H-3-hydroxy-4-oxoquinoline 2,4-dioxygenase, to perform O_2 -dependent oxygenolytic catalysis. The work highlighted how evolution repurposed multiple structural elements of the ABH fold to enable the transition from hydrolytic to oxygenolytic function [44]. Comparison of DhaA 238Loc to extant *Renilla* luciferase (RLuc8), ancestral proteins

with luciferase activity (Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, AncINS, AncFT), and HLDs (LinB, DhaA, DbjA, DmmA, DmmarA, DhIA) reveal several shared and divergent structural features. One of the key determinants of luciferase activity and spectral properties in ABH-fold enzymes is the position and role of residue Asp162 at the rim of the active site cavity. In RLuc8 and AncFT, this aspartate (Asp160) plays a critical role in modulating the electronic state of the CEI product. Specifically, it acts as a nucleophile, stabilizing the 6-*p*-hydroxyphenolate anion of CEI and fine-tuning the emission wavelength [5]. However, the equivalent Asp162 residue in DhaA 238Loc is rotated outward, shifted by one residue in 3D structure and does not interact with the bound substrate. Instead, this position is occupied by Ile163, potentially reducing the stabilization of a negatively charged CEI emitter. This structural rearrangement suggests a partial loss of the spectral-tuning mechanism present in the more specialized luciferases.

In addition to Asp162, DhaA 238Loc features an aromatic cluster formed by Phe262 and Phe263, the same π -stacking residues that line the CTZ-binding pocket in RLuc8. These residues, rare in typical dehalogenases, likely help stabilize the substrate via hydrophobic and π - π interactions, facilitating luciferase activity [5]. The stabilizing effect of Phe262 and Phe263 on luciferin was confirmed by computing interaction energies from MD simulation data. A comparable π - π stacking pattern is observed in AncFT, where the 8-benzyl group of azaCTZ interacts with Phe259 and Phe260, while the hydroxyl group of the 6-*p*-hydroxyphenyl moiety forms a hydrogen bond with Asp160. Such interactions highlight the critical synergy between aromatic residues and catalytic side chains in stabilizing high-energy intermediates and fine-tuning colour of emitted light.

Furthermore, residues in the L9 and L16 loops, notably Trp153, Trp156, Phe261, and Phe262 in RLuc8, have been shown to regulate active site openness and impact activity, with mutagenesis studies confirming a 2- to 3-fold decrease in luminescence [5]. DhaA 238Loc

(caption on next page)

Fig. 8. MD-based analysis and comparison of DhaA 238Loc with RLuc8, AncFT-L14, and Anc^{HLD-RLuc}. **(a)** The potential of mean force used to pull CTZ into the active site of luciferases obtained by adaptive steered MD. **(b)** CTZ end-pose (green sticks) from the simulation of binding to DhaA 238Loc (white cartoon), showing a crystallographic ligand as reference (translucent pale-yellow sticks, PDB ID 7ome). **(c)** The equilibrium probabilities of coelenteramide (CEI) macrostates based on the CEI-active site distance (“bound”, “tunnel”, “unbound”) from the adaptive sampling of CEI unbinding. The simulations were started from the crystal-like CEI pose for each enzyme, plus from the flipped pose in Anc^{HLD-RLuc}. The error bars indicate the standard deviation of the equilibrium probability from bootstrapping a random 80% of the data 100 times. **(d)** Analysis of access tunnels with CAVER Analyst on 1000 dynamic snapshots of luciferase structures. Main tunnels, shown as the bigger circles, have wider average bottlenecks and were present in over 99% of snapshots. In comparison, the side tunnels are shown as smaller, lighter circles, have narrower average bottlenecks, and are less common (percentages next to the circles). **(e, f)** The interaction energies of CEI per residue of **(e)** the “bound” CEI macrostate and **(f)** the “tunnel” macrostate from adaptive sampling with RLuc8, AncFT-L14, and DhaA 238Loc. For clarity, only attractive interactions are shown (< -1.0 kcal·mol⁻¹ for the “bound” states and < -0.5 kcal·mol⁻¹ for the “tunnel” states). The error bars indicate the standard error. **(g, h, i)** Comparison of active-site cavity volumes in DhaA 238Loc, luciferase RLuc8, dual-function ancestral proteins (Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, AncINS, AncFT), and HLDs (DhIA, LinB, DbjA, DmmaA, DbeA, DmmarA), calculated using FPocketWeb **(g)**, CAVER Analyst with hydrogen atoms **(h)**, and without hydrogen atoms **(i)**.

Fig. 9. Experimental validation of molecular determinants identifying luciferase activity. **(a)** Point mutations in the DhaA 238Loc^{Mut} variant relative to the DhaA 238Loc template; the catalytic glutamate (E) is indicated by a star. **(b)** SDS-PAGE analysis confirming the purity and homogeneity of the purified enzymes. **(c)** Circular dichroism (CD) spectra verifying the protein secondary structure. Thermal unfolding profiles as measured by **(d)** NanoDSF and **(g)** CD. **(e, f)** Functional assays showing **(e)** luciferase activity and **(f)** dehalogenase activity measurements. Data indicate the average relative luciferase **(e)** and dehalogenase **(f)** activities of each enzyme variant (DhaA 238Loc = 100%). Assays were done in triplicate; error bars represent standard deviations.

partially mirrors this architecture, especially with bulky aromatic residues in corresponding loops, suggesting increased flexibility and substrate accessibility compared to canonical dehalogenases. Additionally, the Ser145 backbone carbonyl (equivalent to RLuc8) is positioned to form a hydrogen bond with CEI, potentially contributing to the transient stabilization of the emitter state.

To place DhaA 238Loc in a functional context, we used molecular modelling to compare its substrate binding and product release to RLuc8, AncFT-L14, and Anc^{HLD-RLuc}. ASMD simulations showed that luciferin binding to DhaA 238Loc is not more difficult than in the two specialized luciferases, RLuc8 and AncFT-L14, unlike Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, which has the greatest energetic barrier. Adaptive sampling MD of product release confirmed that the product remains tightly bound in DhaA 238Loc, whereas RLuc8 and AncFT-L14 release CEI more readily. Together, these findings indicate that substrate access is not a limiting

factor in DhaA 238Loc, but slow product release likely lowers its overall turnover relative to modern luciferases.

Together, these structural and dynamical features point toward an evolutionary transition in DhaA 238Loc, where luciferase activity is enabled through partial specialization of the binding pocket, even without a full optimization for light emission.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marika Majerova: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jana Horackova:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Karolina Sedlackova:** Methodology, Investigation. **Marie Sulova:** Methodology, Investigation. **David Kovar:** Methodology, Investigation. **Jiri Damborsky:** Validation,

Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Zbynek Prokop:** Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization. **David Bednar:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Martin Marek:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2026.151870>.

Data availability

All molecular dynamics simulations of DhaA 238Loc, Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, RLuc8, and AncFT-L14 are available in Zenodo repository (doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15516240>). Atomic coordinates and structural factors have been saved in the Protein Data Bank under PDB ID accession codes: 9RBN and 9RBP.

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